

REPRESENTATION OF THE CONCEPTS OF "HUMAN AND NATURE" IN THE WORKS OF DORIS LESSING

Alizhonova Okila Alimovna

PhD, researcher in Jizzakh Pedagogical University

Representation of the concepts "Man and Nature" in the novels of Doris Lessing.

e-mail: okila7777@gmail.com

Abstract: This article examines the interpretation of the concepts of "nature and man" in the works of English writer Doris Lessing. Lessing, in his works, deeply analyzes the complex relationship between man and nature, showing the interdependence between these two concepts. In his works, nature appears not only as a background, but as an integral part of human life. Lessing sees nature as an important factor in the formation of the human psyche and psychology, which leads to the study of the interaction between the inner world of man and the external environment in his works.

Keywords: Doris Lessing, literature, nature, human, dependence, mental state, problems, life, psychology.

Among the numerous themes in Doris Lessing's early prose, the understanding of humanity and the surrounding nature dominate. The peculiarities of the artistic representation of these issues in the works of her early short fiction are the focus of this article. The relationship between nature and humanity in the stories from Doris Lessing's African period defines the internal space of the literary work, becomes a key aspect of the plot's development, significantly influences the formation and development of the characters, and constitutes the essence of the author's concept. Therefore, it is possible to speak about the emergence of the concepts of "nature" and "humanity" in Doris Lessing's early prose.

Although Lessing acknowledges the falseness and inconsistency of the myth of the empty land, she recognizes that there is an element of primordiality and wildness in this region, which challenges, frightens, but also attracts settlers. In her stories, the author shows that this phenomenon can be observed even on farms with cultivated land. It can be confidently stated that the first shade of primordiality, wildness (the first component or layer according to Y.S. Stepanov) of the concept of "nature" in Doris Lessing's stories emerges from the existing socio-linguistic and historical peculiarities. Therefore, paying close attention to the concept of "nature" not only allows for the analysis of Lessing's stance toward the natural world but also:

1. examines how the writer depicts the wildness and unexplored areas of Africa, and through this presents a complete and complex picture of the settler society in her stories;
2. demonstrates how the author shows different types of relationships between the settlers and the wild African landscape, and how this characterizes them (which brings forth the concept of "human");
3. identifies the differences between settlers and indigenous people, primarily in their relationship with nature (which brings forth the concept of "human");
4. determines the value of this wild land for Doris Lessing and the place of humans within it, i.e., outlining the role and significance of the concepts of "nature" and "human" in the early stories of Doris Lessing.

Nature and humanity in Doris Lessing's stories are in constant interaction, typically being the driving forces that shape the plot's development. The primary component of the concept of "nature" — primordially, wildness, untamed — can also be applied to humans. The concept of "human" in Lessing's works always carries a dual nature, presenting contrasts: "settler" – "indigenous person." Each of these has a dual possible reading: "settler" – "civilized"/"colonial"; "indigenous person" – "native" / "savage." Each of the two variations of the "human" concept has its own distinct features. For example, some of the settlers depicted in Lessing's works refuse to stay in a house for long and prefer to roam the bush under the starry sky, "subjugating the wild nature to themselves." The indigenous people, although they live in their homes, differ from the settlers in their closeness to the natural environment. Their knowledge of wild plants, for instance, can be seen in the story *No Witchcraft for Sale*, in which the servant Gideon heals a boy's eyes with plants from the bush. Gideon perceives the "bush" not as an unexplored wilderness, but as a well-known territory. The component of wildness, untamed nature in the concept of "nature," in the sense of "uncivilized," is brought into Africa through the settler culture, marking the perspectives of the continent in terms of its explored state, reflecting the settler's experience. As we can see, it is the colonial context of the stories that introduces the component of primordial wildness of the environment into the concept of "nature," thereby reflecting one of the goals of colonial politics — "taming," "subduing" this wild land to bring it under control.

Thanks to the component of primordial wildness in the environment, the concept of "nature" in Doris Lessing's works becomes one of the most important aspects of portraying the colonial world. Through the description of the relationship between settlers and nature, the surrounding world, the author manages to recreate the mentality of contemporary colonizers, showing their true attitude toward Africa and dismantling the stereotype of the settler created in society. Thus, Lessing's use of the concept of "nature" provides an opportunity to see the weaknesses of settler society and demonstrates its complexity and ambiguity. The author's stance reflects Doris Lessing's critical view of many aspects of the life of white settlers.

The concept of "nature" in Lessing's works is presented as a complex system: depictions of nature are conveyed through the narrator, who focuses the reader's attention on them in the text. These descriptions of nature serve as an indirect, intricate structure of primary reality, which, in turn, conveys important information about the narrator and the characters who come into focus within the narrative. Their perception and evaluation of the surrounding nature provide clear insights into their origins and cultural values. In this way, the concept of "nature" modulates various manifestations of the concept of "human." This was confirmed in an interview with Doris Lessing in 1964, where she emphasized that her stories address not only the issue of "colored populations" but also the impact of the natural world on the human world:

"Back then, I wrote short stories set in the region where I grew up, where isolated white farmers lived far apart on their properties... People who could have been perfectly ordinary citizens in a society like English society, to which they were supposed to conform, could become completely wild eccentrics, something they wouldn't have dared to be anywhere else... I don't think my memory is deceiving me, but I think people of 'colored races' would return to South Rhodesia due to the impossibility of finding living space for themselves" [7: 3].

In Doris Lessing's works, the interconnection of the concepts of "nature and humanity" is expressed deeply and complexly. In her works, nature is considered an inseparable part of human life, further enhancing the interaction between the internal and external worlds of a person. Lessing presents nature not only as a backdrop but also as an important factor in shaping the human psyche.

Her works address themes such as the relationship between nature and humanity, ecological issues, and humanity's responsibility toward nature. Lessing emphasizes the need for a change in humanity's attitude toward nature and urges readers to deepen their understanding of the relationship between nature and humanity.

So, in the works of Doris Lessing, through its exploration of the relationship between nature and humanity, focuses on environmental issues in contemporary literature and highlights the need to increase humanity's responsibility toward nature. This, in turn, helps students better understand the complex relationships between nature and humanity.

References

1. Askoldov-Alekseyev, S. A. Concept and Word / S. A. Askoldov-Alekseyev // Russian Literature: From the Theory of Literature to the Structure of the Text: Anthology / [edited by V. P. Nerosznak]. – Moscow: Academia, 1997. – Pp. 267–279.
2. Likhachev, D. S. The Conceptosphere of the Russian Language / D. S. Likhachev // Essays on the Philosophy of Artistic Creativity / Russian Academy of Sciences, Institute of Russian Literature (Pushkin House). – St. Petersburg: BLITZ, 1999. – Pp. 147–165.
3. Stepanov, Y. S. Constants: Dictionary of Russian Culture (3rd edition, revised and expanded) – Moscow: Akademicheskii Proyekt, 2004. – 992 p.
4. Bertelsen, E. (1991). Veldanschauung: Doris Lessing's Savage Africa. *Modern Fiction Studies*, 37(4), Pp. 647–658.
5. Chennells, A. (1985). Doris Lessing: Rhodesian Novelist. *Doris Lessing Newsletter*, 9(2), 3-7.
6. Hunter, E. (1990). A Sense of Place in Selected African Works by Doris Lessing. Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Cape Town.
7. Ingersoll, E. G. (1994). Putting the Questions Differently: Interviews with Doris Lessing 1964–1994. London: Flamingo.
8. Lessing, D. (1992). This Was the Old Chief's Country (Collected African Stories, Vol. 1) // Doris Lessing. – London: Paladin, 1992. – 322 p.
9. Lessing, D. (1994). The Sun Between Their Feet (Collected African Stories, Vol. 2) // Doris Lessing. – London: Flamingo, 1994. – 380 p.
10. Whittaker, R. (1988). *Doris Lessing*. London: Macmillan.
11. Amanullaeva Kamola Muminovna. National concepts and their literary representation in Haruki Murakami's novel "IQ84" *Wschodnioeuropejskie Czasopismo Naukowe (East European Scientific Journal) № 9(25), 2017.*
<https://sciencescholar.us/journal/index.php/ijhs/article/view/11004>
12. Амануллаева Камола Муминовна. Художественный концепт и специфические характеристики его воссоздания, *Хорижий филология №4, Самарқанд. СамДЧТИ. 2020, Б.53-57.* https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/foreign_philology/article/view/1579
13. Amanullayeva Kamola Muminovna, Universal concept as structural formation of the component of Haruki Murakami's novel "Kafka on the Shore" *Jour of Adv research in Dynamical & Control Systems, Vol. 12, Issue- 2020, Scopus, Б.1117-1121.*
<https://sciencescholar.us/journal/index.php/ijhs/article/view/11004>
14. Amanullayeva Kamola Muminovna, The literary concept as of the creative process in the literary comprehension, *ЎЗМУ ХАБАРЛАРИ. Тошкент-2021. Б.179-181.*

15. Амануллаева Камола Муминовна. О художественном концепте и в целом, Россия и Узбекистан Международные образовательные научные и социально–культурные технологии: векторы развития Челябинск-Ташкент-Бухара-Самарканд 2020. Б.271-272.
16. Амануллаева Камола Муминовна. О воссоздании художественного концепта в переводе между разносистемных языков. Хорижий филология, адабиётшунослик ва таржимашунослик масалалари. Республика илмий-амалий конференцияси. Жиззах. 2021, Б.9-12.
17. Амануллаева Камола Муминовна. Теоретическая интерпретация понятия концептосферы. Самарканд. №4, СамДЧТИ. 2021, Б.120-126.
18. Амануллаева Камола Муминовна. Матн тузилишида бадий концепт. Буюк ипак йўлида умуминсоний ва миллий қадриятлар: тил, таълим ва маданият. Халқаро илмий-амалий конференция. Самарканд. 2022, Б. 499-501.
19. Амануллаева Камола Муминовна. XX-XXI асрларда таржима. Хорижий тил таълими лингводидактикаси ва инновацион асослари. Халқаро илмий-амалий конференция. Самарканд. 2022, 212-214 б.
20. Amanullayeva K. M. Badiiy asar konseptosferasi va asosiy konseptlarning tarjimada qayta yaratilishi. Samarqand-2020.
21. Amanullayeva Kamola “Tokio afsonalari”, Харуки Murakami hikoyalarining tarjimalari, 2017, 104b.
22. Amanullayeva Kamola Muminovna. The role of translation in science. Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History. 2023, 60-62 p.
23. Amanullayeva Kamola Muminovna. The concept of translation and characteristics of fetures. Information Horizons: American Journal of Library and Information Science. 2024, 63-66 p.
24. Nasrullayeva Tozagul Suxrobovna, Amanullayeva Kamola Muminovna. Peculiarities of translation of Technical Terms, Concepts and Rendering articles in technical translation. American journal of social and humanitarian research, 2023. –С.29-33.
25. Kubayeva Nafisa, Amanullayeva Kamola. The problem of teaching students lexical and phraseological features in translation studies of phrasel verbs in English and Uzbek languages. Eurasian journal of academic research. 39-42 p. <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/37844>
26. О.А.Алижонова, К.М.Амануллаева, М.Б.Аскарлова. Использование термин концепт в лингвокультурологии. Вестник магистратуры. 2024.№12-2 (159) С.76-78